

Preliminary Analysis of Copenhagen Set Simulation Run M11

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Definition of Set

Parameters for the simulation were defined by Zeis 82-11-05 (MAT-HIP-03613).
Main characteristics are:

- Random, uniform star distribution; mean density 2.457 deg^{-2}
- Magnitude distribution over $5 < B < 13$ in proportion to the star numbers in ESA's System Requirements (RFQ/3-4588/82/NL/MD - Doc. I-A), p. 40
- Duration of set 12 h (six great circle scans); frame period 2 s
- Time allocation within each frame in proportion to the "observing time per star" in the System Requirements, p. 40
- No occultations or other (intentional) interruptions
- No determination of basic angle or other distortion parameters
- Mean error for 1 s observation: $\sigma_{\eta}(B, 1s) = 7.2 \cdot 10^{0.2(B-9)} \text{ mas}$

Number of observations etc

The set simulation resulted in 82,827 observations of 2109 stars in 19,502 frames (Petersen, private comm. 83-02-23). One star was unconnected and one was used to define the abscissa origin, so statistics below are for 2107 stars.

It may be interesting to compare these numbers with expectations. With a revolving velocity of 13 am/h, the set covers about 846 deg^2 . The expected number of stars is then 2080, in good agreement with the simulation. The total number of frames is $(12 \text{ h})/(2 \text{ s}) = 21,600$, but some of these contain less than 2 stars and are not retained. Assuming that the star numbers per frame (m) obey Poisson statistics (as they should in this case), the expected number of frames with $m = 0$ or 1 is

$$21,600 \times (1 + \mu) \exp(-\mu) = 2010$$

where $\mu = 2 \times 0.9^2 \times 2.457 = 3.98$ is the average number of stars in the FOV. The actual number of discarded frames is $21,600 - 19,502 = 2098$, also in fair agreement. As for the number of observations, I assume that frames with $m < 2$ produce no observations, $2 \leq m \leq 10$ give m observations, and $m > 10$ gives 10 observations per frame. The expected number of observations is then

$$21,600 \left[\sum_{m=2}^{10} m \frac{\mu^m}{m!} e^{-\mu} + \sum_{m=11}^{\infty} 10 \frac{\mu^m}{m!} e^{-\mu} \right] = 84,275$$

or about 1500 greater than the actual number. The difference seems to be significant but I have no explanation of it.

Observation mean errors

To estimate the average observation error as function of B, I have simulated 1000 frames with an average of $82,827/19,502 = 4.25$ stars with the required magnitude distribution. Resulting average $\sigma_{\eta}(B, \tau)$ and corresponding τ are given below.

B	f(B)	$\sigma_{\eta}(B, \tau)$	τ
5.5	0.030	3.13 mas	0.211 s
6.5	0.054	4.73	0.232
7.5	0.148	6.74	0.287
8.5	0.408	9.47	0.365
9.5	0.160	13.3	0.467
10.5	0.120	18.6	0.600
11.5	0.060	27.0	0.710
12.5	0.020	39.8	0.823
all	1.000	12.0 mas	0.416 s

The number of observations per star ranges from 9 (one FOV passage) to 108 (12 passages); the average is $\langle n \rangle = 82,827/2109 = 39.3$. I estimate that $\langle n^{-1/2} \rangle = 0.178$.

Results: rms abscissa error versus magnitude

The abscissa errors (a_i) were grouped by Petersen in magnitude intervals and the averages and standard deviations computed:

$$\langle a \rangle(B) = \sum_{i \in B} a_i / N(B) \quad \sigma_a(B) = \left[\sum_{i \in B} [a_i - \langle a \rangle(B)]^2 / [N(B) - 1] \right]^{1/2}$$

In the table below I have added the estimated s.d. of $\sigma_a(B)$, computed as $\sigma_a(B) [2N(B)]^{-1/2}$.

B	N(B)	$\langle a \rangle(B)$	$\sigma_a(B)$	s.d. of $\sigma_a(B)$
5 - 6	62	1.86 mas	4.89 mas	0.43 mas
6 - 7	105	1.98	4.59	0.32
7 - 8	275	1.87	4.13	0.18
8 - 9	887	2.33	5.15	0.12
9 - 10	342	2.40	5.31	0.20
10 - 11	274	2.54	6.33	0.27
11 - 12	127	2.86	6.66	0.42
12 - 13	35	3.46	9.35	1.12
all	2107	2.33 mas	5.32 mas	0.08 mas

The trend in $\langle a \rangle(B)$ appears very convincing but must be ascribed to chance. None of the eight values differs significantly from the overall average (2.33 mas).

Analysing the relation between σ_η and σ_a as in NDAC/LO/017 (p. 7), I find

$$H = \frac{\langle \sigma_a \rangle}{\langle \sigma_\eta \rangle \langle n^{-1/2} \rangle} = 2.49 \pm 0.06$$

$$h = 0.28 \pm 0.03$$

See Figure 1.

Results: rms abscissa error versus number of observations

From the printout of n_i , a_i for all 2107 stars I computed the rms dispersion of a_i from the mean value 2.33 mas for a few intervals in n_i . (Lack of time and energy prevented me from grouping all stars in n_i -intervals.) Results are shown in the table below. The resulting H-value is of course the same as before, but the regression of σ_a versus $\langle \sigma_\eta \rangle n^{-1/2}$, with $\langle \sigma_\eta \rangle = 12.0$ mas, gives

$$h = 1.06 \pm 0.05$$

(weighted least-squares fit). An unweighted fit gives $h = 0.75$. A value of $h = 1$ (dashed line in Figure 2) means that $\sigma_a \propto n^{-1/2}$.

n_i	$n_i^{-\frac{1}{2}}$	N_{star}	$\sigma_a = (a_i - 2.33)_{\text{rms}}$	s.d. of σ_a
9	0.333	126	7.39 mas	0.47 mas
10 - 19	0.239	347	7.69	0.29
all	0.178	2107	5.32	0.08
40 - 49	0.149	218	4.09	0.20
85 - 94	0.106	48	3.33	0.34
100 - 109	0.097	81	2.13	0.17

Discussion

It is natural to compare M11 with M4, which is similar in length (12 h), number of stars, and number of observations (cf. NDAC/LO/017). The main differences are

- (i) that the SAO catalogue with cut-off at $V = 8.7$ was used for M4, but a synthetic (random) catalogue for M11;
- (ii) that the stars have a much wider magnitude distribution in M11;
- (iii) that the formula for $\sigma_\eta(B, 1s)$ is different in the two simulations, giving a larger $\langle \sigma_\eta \rangle$ in M11 but also a much wider distribution;
- (iv) that no instrument parameters are determined in M11, while 11 distortion terms (including the basic angle) are included in M4.

Simulation run M4 gave $H = 1.78$ and $h = 0.40$. The h -value was practically the same for σ_a versus magnitude (σ_η) as for σ_a versus number of observations ($n^{-\frac{1}{2}}$).

The set reduction formula (017.5) introducing H and h was formulated with the intention of making H and h independent of the values and distributions of σ_η and n . Therefore, (ii) and (iii) above should not affect H and h very much. On the other hand, (i) and (iv) should work in the direction of making M4 less rigid than M11 (non-uniform star distribution; several instrument parameters), so I would have expected $H \lesssim 1.8$ for M11. The value $H = 2.49$ actually obtained means that the abscissa errors are about 40 % larger than expected, which is indeed very serious. Also the large difference in h between the regressions versus σ_η and versus $n^{-\frac{1}{2}}$ is surprising, indicating that the set reduction formula in NDAC/LO/017 is totally inadequate.

Both the average size of abscissa errors and their distribution with respect to B and n are so different from previous simulations and experience, that I can only conclude that there is some serious error in M11.

FIGURE 1. Rms abscissa error vs σ_η (B); fixed $n^{-0.5} = 0.178$

FIGURE 2. Rms abscissa error vs $n^{-0.5}$; fixed $\sigma_\eta = 12.0$ mas